

THE IMPACT OF FULL DAY KINDERGARTEN SYSTEM ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT.

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Abstract: This article is about early education and development. Furthermore, this article provides information about the effects of kindergarten on children's academic achievement and socioemotional improvement.

Key words: kindergarten, early childhood education, academic and social content, school readiness, modern methods.

The kindergarten method of teaching is nurturing and supportive rather than competitive. Children learn through fun and engaging activities like art and music, transforming playtime into opportunities to instill important cognitive skills and social skills. There are different opinions about language learning and teaching in kindergartens. According to Childcare and Preschool Development in Europe: Present day tendencies in the development of pre-school organizations have their roots in different national traditions, themselves having their origins in different eras of social and economic development. These traditions have been crystallized in different institutions, in socially and legally structured ways of doing things which tend to facilitate the introduction of some innovations, and to stand in the way of others (1).

The kindergarten system establishes a relationship between the children and the teacher in which they feel secure and know the teacher is a guide and friend. Then this system helps to understand each child as a person and to further his or her development in light of his or her own personality that he or she may live as a corporate person in a social group. Moreover, there is the curriculum grow out of the interests the children bring to school from their home and community living. (2)

Dewey called for educational activities that would support continuity in children's growth and would be connected to their everyday lives.

Most of the recent research on all-day kindergarten indicates positive benefits for children in terms of academic achievement and behavior but what children do in kindergarten may be more important than how long they are in the classroom each day. (3)

Experts now are in general agreement that there are no detrimental effects to attending full-day kindergarten and, in fact, students in full-day programs show significantly stronger academic gains over the course of the kindergarten than their half-day counterparts. The research also finds that poor and minority students especially can benefit from participation in full-day programs. There is less agreement about the degree to which benefits gained from attending full-day kindergarten carry forward throughout the student's academic career. (4)

Although children's curiosity is thought to be important for early learning, the association of curiosity with early academic achievement has not been tested. We hypothesized that greater curiosity would be associated with greater kindergarten academic achievement in reading and math.

Uzbekistan is currently undergoing radical changes in the system of preschool education. In particular, radical reforms are being implemented in the field of pre-school education and new decisions and regulations are being developed. However, the analysis shows that the

effectiveness and results of work carried out in the field of kindergarten system, along with the achievements, as well as problems. Over the past 20 years, the number of state-owned preschools has decreased by more than 45% and today the coverage of children with preschool education in the country is 30%. Additionally, the material and technical base of kindergarten education institutions does not meet modern requirements. (5)

In conclusion, kindergarten education is the primary link in the system of continuing education, which plays a vital role in the education and preparation of a healthy and mature child in all respects. The effective use of modern methods, pedagogical technologies contributes to the development of the field and the personal, emotional, speech, mathematical, physical and creative development of children.

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